

Some Peculiarities of Integration of Language and Culture in Teaching Process

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Abstract: Language always carries meanings and references beyond itself: the meanings of a particular language represent the culture of a particular social group. Interacting with a language means doing it with a culture, which is its point of reference. We could not understand a culture without having direct access to its language because of their close connection.

Keywords: language teaching, human communication, human interaction, cultural products, communicative power.

INTRODUCTION. A specific language indicates the culture of a particular social group. Thus, learning a language is not only the study of the alphabet, meaning, grammar rules and the arrangement of words, but also the study of the behavior of society and its cultural customs. Thus, language teaching should always contain some explicit reference to the culture, the whole from which a particular language is extracted. The process of human communication is complicated because many of our messages are transmitted through a para-language. These auxiliary communication methods are culturally specific, so communicating with people from other societies or ethnic groups is fraught with the danger of misunderstanding if the broader cultural structure is ignored. Growing up in a certain society, we informally learn to use gestures, looks, small changes in tone or voice, and other auxiliary means of communication to change or emphasize what we say and do. We have been mastering these culturally specific methods for many years, mainly through observation and imitation.

METHODOLOGY. English language learning has become a global phenomenon, with millions of learners around the world seeking to acquire proficiency in this lingua franca. One of the key factors influencing English language learning is culture. This paper critically examines the role of culture in English language learning and identifies the challenges and opportunities that language educators face in incorporating culture into their teaching methodologies. The review draws on a comprehensive analysis of existing literature and research, highlighting the significance of culture in language learning and providing practical recommendations for language educators to create culturally inclusive and effective language learning environments. The most obvious form of para-language is body language, or kinesics, which is the language of gestures, expressions, and poses. However, the meaning of words can also be changed by the tone and character of the voice. Language and culture have complex, homologous relationships. Language is intricately intertwined with culture (they developed together, influencing each other in the process, eventually shaping what it

means to be human). In this context, AL Krober said: "Thus, culture began when speech appeared, and since then the enrichment of one means the further development of the other."

If culture is a product of human interaction, then cultural manifestations are acts of communication that are accepted by certain speech communities. According to Rossi Landi "the totality of messages that we exchange with each other when speaking a given language constitutes a speech community, that is, the whole society, understood from the point of view of speaking." He further explains that all children learn their language from their societies, and in the process of learning the language they also learn their culture and develop their cognitive abilities.

Language communicates through culture, and culture also communicates through language: Michael Silverstein suggested that the communicative power of culture works not only in representing aspects of reality, but also in linking one context to another. That is, communication is not only the use of symbols that "denote" beliefs, feelings, identities or events, it is also a way of bringing beliefs, feelings and identities into the current context.

According to the principle of linguistic relativity, the way we think about the world directly depends on the language we use to talk about it. "The real world is largely unconsciously built on the group's language habits. There are no two languages that are so similar as to represent the same social reality. The worlds in which different societies live are different, not just the same with a different label attached" (Edward Sapir, 1929). Therefore, speaking means assuming culture, and knowing culture is the same as knowing a language. Language and culture are homologous mental realities. Cultural products are representations and interpretations of the world that must be transmitted in order to be lived. Intercultural competence is one of the language learning outcomes in addition to linguistic proficiency (Byram, 1997). Teachers who receive intercultural competence training are better able to handle the variety of cultural dynamics that arise in the classroom (Kramsch, 2013). It is not only about teaching language; it is also about developing an awareness of various cultural viewpoints in order to better equip pupils to deal with the challenges of a globalized world. This essay examines the difficulties and possibilities faced by teachers when incorporating technology, culture, and a range of student backgrounds into language instruction. The culture section explores the role of culture in promoting efficient communication, the impact of linguistic stereotypes, and the importance of cultural material in language learning (Byram et al., 2002; Pennycook, 2007). It is not enough for educators to comprehend these aspects; they also need to actively apply this understanding to their teaching methods, dispelling myths and creating a climate where good intercultural communication is valued.

The advantages of integrating digital tools, online resources, and language learning platforms into language instruction are examined in the section on technology integration (Huber, 2008; Levy & Stockwell, 2006). Additionally, it looks at how technology supports individualized learning, cultural interchange, and language practice (Reinders, 2012; Thorne & Payne, 2005). Teachers need to carefully incorporate technology into the classroom so that it becomes an essential component of learning, not just an add-on, rather than just acknowledging its advantages.

RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS. The problem is what happens when cross-cultural interaction occurs, i.e. when the producer and recipient of the message belong to different cultures. Contacts between cultures are increasing, and intercultural communication is becoming mandatory for those who want to get along and understand those whose beliefs and backgrounds may differ greatly from their own.

Language can mark cultural identity, but it is also used to denote other phenomena and to denote what is beyond itself, especially when a particular speaker uses it to explain intentions. A specific language indicates the culture of a particular social group. Therefore,

we can assume that language learning is cultural learning, therefore language teaching is cultural learning due to the interdependence of language and cultural learning. Culture is a fuzzy set of attitudes, beliefs, behavioral conventions, basic assumptions and values that are shared by a group of people and that influence the behavior of each member and the interpretation by each member of the meanings of other people's behavior. And language is a means of expressing and embodying other phenomena. It expresses the values, beliefs and meanings that members of a given society share by virtue of their socialization in it. Language also refers to objects peculiar to a given culture, as evidenced by proper names embodying these objects. Byran argued that a "loaf of bread" evokes a certain culture of objects in British usage, unless a conscious effort is made to purge it of this reference and introduce a new one. Thus, we can conclude that language is a part of culture, and through it we can express cultural beliefs and values, and that the specific uses of this word are peculiar to language and its connection with culture.

CONCLUSION. In fact, teaching a language inevitably means teaching a language and culture. According to Boutiest, "The study of culture is actually a key factor in the ability to use and master a foreign language system." The Bellagio Declaration of the European Cultural Foundation and the International Council for the Development of Education states: "For effective international cooperation, knowledge of other countries and their cultures is just as important as knowledge of their languages, and such knowledge depends on teaching foreign languages."

The study of language, therefore, is the study of the behavior of a given society and its cultural customs. Language is a product of society's thinking and behavior. The effectiveness of an individual native speaker in a foreign language is directly related to his/her understanding of the culture of that language (Taylor, 1979), and one can consider teaching culture through students' own languages, which can be used in a certain way to interpret another culture (Ager).

Finally, we can conclude that immersion learning accelerates the acquisition of cultural knowledge: "... the integration of language and culture learning by using language as a means for continuous socialization of students is a process that is not intended to imitate and copy the socialization of native-speaking teachers, but rather to develop the cultural competence of students from its existing stage, turning it into an intercultural competence"

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